

FEATURES OF ACCOUNTING FOR ARREARS ON PAYMENTS TO THE BUDGET IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. In the conditions of the modern formation of market relations, in the course of settlements of an organization with other persons, depending on the economic situation, it has relations with counterparties - debtors and creditors. The financial crisis has caused a rapid increase in the optimization of the system of settlements with counterparties, since unregulated outflows of funds, attraction of cheap borrowed funds, can negatively affect the financial stability of the organization, causing a liquidity crisis.

Keywords: debt accounting, budget payments, accounts receivable, accounts payable.

Introduction.

The problem of the economy and the monetary sphere is also relevant during the crisis – the problem of non-payments, which causes huge problems both for enterprises individually and for the economy as a whole. Currently, the state of mutual settlements of enterprises is due to the high share of accounts receivable in the structure of their current assets. This can lead to a decrease in solvency and financial stability, an increase in debt collection costs and, accordingly, a decrease in return on capital. And accounts receivable, which arose as a result of late payment of products to customers, leads to the extraction of financial resources of the organization, and can cause poor performance of capital turnover. Therefore, economic control over the organization of settlement relations, the state of payment discipline, the dynamics of accounts receivable and accounts payable

plays a huge role in strengthening the financial position and solvency of the organization. And the correct organization of accounting for accounts receivable and accounts payable ensures not only the survival of the company, but also its sustainable development, allows to increase the efficiency of management as a whole. Tracking and monitoring the state of accounts payable can become an additional and cheap source of borrowing. Therefore, it is equally important to build the right relationships with counterparties, exercising constant control over the movement of receivables and payables, observing the trend of its changes in the medium and long term. Knowledge of the legal basis for the formation of receivables and payables is of great importance. Economic reforms put forward increased demands on it. The correct orientation in making ordinary decisions depends on rationally organized accounting, which ensures the timeliness and quality of accounting information.

International requirements for the composition, content and disclosure of accounting information establish the fundamental criteria for the quality of the accountant's performance. The company's financial statements are a "product" of the accounting system. The daily activities of accounting specialists are aimed at obtaining this "product" that meets the necessary requirements: completeness, reliability, timeliness, usefulness, objectivity, etc. Consideration of individual examples of foreign and domestic accounting practice, allows us to identify the most pressing problems associated with the implementation in the Republic of Uzbekistan of the principles of preparation and preparation of financial statements based on international and national standards. Separate accounting procedures used in foreign accounting are also characteristic of domestic practice. Examples of this kind of accounting objects are accounting for arrears on payments to the budget.

Debt is the amount of monetary obligations payable by the subject of the

credit history provided for by the credit transaction. Debt - debt on payments to the republican and (or) local budgets (hereinafter referred to as the budget), debt on loans issued by state banks.

Arrears on payments to the budget – the amount of taxes, fees (duties), fines, penalties and other payments not paid on time, payable to the budget in accordance with the legislation, including payments for repayment of arrears on budget loans, budget loans, interest on budget loans, penalties accrued for late repayment such loans and loans, on fulfilled guarantees.

Payments to the budget – tax revenues, non-tax revenues, gratuitous receipts, funds issued (received) on a refundable basis, as well as those received in order to attract sources of financing the budget deficit.

Summarizing information about the company's current obligations on payments to the budget is carried out on account 6410 "Arrears on payments to the budget (by type)". According to the credit of account 6410 "Arrears on payments to the budget (by type)", the amount due to the contribution to the budget is reflected in correspondence with accounts receivable, accounts for accounting for expenses of the period, the use of profits for paying taxes and fees, settlements with staff on wages. At the final calculation, the previously listed advance payments for taxes and fees to the budget are reflected in the debit of account 6410 "Arrears in payments to the budget (by type)" in correspondence with the account for accounting for advance payments to the budget (4400). In fact, the amounts transferred to the budget are reflected in the debit of account 6410 "Arrears in payments to the budget (by type)" in correspondence with cash accounting accounts. Analytical accounting on account 6410 "Arrears on payments to the budget (by type)" it is conducted by type of taxes (Table No. 1).

**Correspondence on accounts of accounting of arrears on
payments to the budget (by type) (6400)**

table 1

№	The content of the business transaction	Correspondence of accounts	
		Debit	Credit
1	Arrears to the budget for various deductions, taxes and fees related to the expenses of the period	9430	6410
2	The amounts of VAT and excise taxes were accrued on the sale of finished products, goods, works performed and services rendered, as well as on the sale and disposal of fixed assets and other assets	4010	6410
3	Funds have been returned from the budget or offset against future payments (with final recalculations, etc.)	5110, 5210, 5530, 4410	6410
4	of the amount of deductions of personal income tax from wages	6710	6410
5	Amounts of tax on income from accrued dividends	6610	6410
6	Accrued payments from profit to budget	9810-9890	6410
7	Payments to the budget are actually transferred	6410	5010-5530
8	VAT related to material resources, goods, works and services is accepted for offset	6410	4410
9	The debt to the budget has been repaid by obtaining loans and loans	6410	6810-6840, 7810-7840

The company's tax liabilities are short-term, since in accordance with the legislation they must be repaid in the current period. Uzbek National Accounting Standard No. 21 provides for such accounts as 4410 "Advance payments on taxes and other mandatory payments to the budget" and 6410 "Arrears on payments to the budget (by type)" to reflect the company's tax obligations.

For analytical accounting, it is recommended to open separate accounts for each type of tax paid:

- 6411 "VAT arrears";
- 6412 "Excise tax arrears";
- 6413 "Income tax arrears" (turnover tax (until 1.01.2020 - single tax payment));
- 6414 "Property tax arrears";
- 6415 "Personal income tax arrears", etc.

In recent years, the problem of managing accounts receivable has intensified, which is primarily due to the slowdown in payment turnover, which causes an increase in accounts receivable. Accounts receivable - the amount of debts owed to the enterprise from legal entities or individuals as a result of economic relations with them. Therefore, the necessary task is the effective management of accounts receivable, aimed at bringing its size to an optimal state and ensuring timely repayment of the debt. Various domestic and foreign scientists have their own views on the interpretation of such concepts as accounts receivable, several of the most well-known ones can be particularly noted. Considering accounts receivable as an asset, N.P. Kondrakov wrote“ "the embodiment of the right to probable future benefits arising from the obligations of third parties”" In the economic encyclopedia of L.I. Abalkin, accounts receivable is understood as "the monetary expression of the debt of individuals and legal entities to this enterprise"¹. The presence of accounts receivable indicates an increase in the company's funds from economic turnover.

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¹ Новый тип экономического мышления / Л. И. Абалкин. — М.: Экономика, 1987. — 189,

on payments to the budget (by type)", the amount due to the contribution to the budget is reflected in correspondence with accounts receivable, accounts for accounting for expenses of the period, the use of profits for taxes and other mandatory payments, settlements with staff on wages. At the final calculation, the previously listed advance payments for taxes and other mandatory payments to the budget are reflected in the debit of account 6410 "Arrears in payments to the budget (by type)" in correspondence with the account for accounting for advance payments to the budget 4400. In fact, the amounts transferred to the budget are reflected in the debit of account 6410 "Arrears in payments to the budget (by type)" in correspondence with cash accounting accounts.

Due to the crisis of payments and the lack of funds on the settlement accounts of enterprises, a significant number of taxpayers are late paying off the budget, have constantly increasing arrears on payments to the budget system.

In these conditions, the executive authorities of the subjects of the Russian Federation and local self-government make decisions:

- on the repayment of arrears in the payment of taxes to the relevant budgets with natural coating (coal, petroleum products, food, etc.);
- on the offsetting between the enterprise - defaulter, budget institution and the local budget;
- on offsetting the debts of territorial budgets to taxpayers under treasury tax exemptions (by analogy with the offsetting of federal budget debts carried out by the Ministry of Finance of Uzbekistan).

Based on the need to reflect such settlement transactions with territorial budgets in tax reporting on the receipt of taxes and other mandatory payments, the State Tax Service of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Finance of Uzbekistan explain.

The basis for the reflection by tax authorities of tax receipts in the form of manufactured products or services, the repayment of arrears in the payment of taxes to territorial budgets and the conduct of offsets should be the relevant resolutions (orders) adopted by the executive authorities of the subjects of the Russian Federation and local administration. At the same time, the following procedure for processing these operations is recommended:

The financial authority, having received documents confirming the release of products, submits to the state tax inspectorate a certificate of payment of taxes, which includes the following details: the date of the operation, the name of the enterprise, the total amount of taxes credited to the territorial budget by the payment dates.

In the accounting for the execution of the local budget, in-kind calculations are reflected as tax receipts and budget expenditures are reflected in the same amount, however, accounting operations are carried out bypassing the current account of the local budget. In the accounting of enterprises paying taxes in kind, such payment must necessarily be reflected on the credit of the accounts for the sale of products (works, services) in correspondence with the debit of the account of settlements with the budget.

To repay accounts payable that were not covered last year, what documents do budget organizations need to issue and to which organization are they provided? In what order is its calculation carried out? Accounts payable in an additional period of time to the financial year are paid according to the expense item of the cost estimate for the past year for which the accounts payable arose.

Budgetary organizations and recipients of budgetary funds for the payment of accounts payable for the past financial year submit the following documents to the relevant treasury departments

Payment schedule in duplicate and application for registration (accounting) of legal obligations;

letter a letter indicating the potential source of funds for the payment of accounts payable, the corresponding personal treasury account and other details;

a copy of the contract for the last fiscal year for which this debt arose;

application application for registration (accounting) of financial obligations and copies of invoices confirming the delivery of goods (performance of works, provision of services);

the applicant's reconciliation report drawn up with the supplier of goods (works, services) (contractor) (taking into account calculations made in an additional period of time);

written written opinion on the provision in the cost estimates for the current financial year of the necessary funds to cover accounts payable (in cases where accounts payable are covered at the expense of budgetary funds);

a payment order executed in accordance with the established procedure, or a memorial order of the Treasury (at the same time, for the purposes of payment, "payment of accounts payable for the past year" is additionally indicated).

The repayment of accounts payable for the month of December last year, postponed to the next year, is carried out at the expense of the budget funds provided for in the cost estimates of the current financial year (taking into account the temporary cost estimates). When filling out payment orders to cover accounts payable in an additional period of time to the financial year and memorial orders of the Treasury, in accordance with the purpose of the payment, the entry "Covering accounts payable for 20__ year" is entered in the payment order and memorial order.

Payment orders or Treasury urgent orders formed to cover accounts payable

for the past year must be submitted to the Treasury departments no later than five working days before the end of the additional period of time for the financial year. Payment orders or Treasury momeria orders formed to cover accounts payable for the past year must be submitted to Treasury departments no later than five working days before the end of the additional period of time to the financial year.

In case of failure to provide payment orders or treasury momeria orders formed to cover accounts payable for the past year, no later than five working days before the end of the additional period of time to the financial year, the funds allocated from the budget lose the established purpose and will be considered the balances of the respective budgets. After the end of the additional period of time to the financial year, the accounts payable of enterprises will primarily be paid at the expense of extra-budgetary funds of the budgetary organization.

In cases of insufficiency or lack of funds in the extra-budgetary funds of a budgetary organization, the accounts payable of the past year will be paid at the expense of the funds provided for in the cost estimates for the current financial year (taking into account time estimates). At the same time, the payment is made only if there is a written conclusion of the distributors of budget funds (for organizations receiving funds from the republican budget), territorial financial authorities on the provision in the cost estimates for the current financial year of the necessary funds to cover accounts payable (based on approved estimates provided by budget organizations and the corresponding calculations for the accounts payable that have arisen).

At the same time, the amount of legal obligations assumed under the corresponding expenditure item for the current fiscal year for budgetary funds is reduced by the amount directed to the payment of accounts payable of the past year. In the contract, the amount of accounts payable under contracts concluded by

budget organizations with suppliers is indicated separately for legal obligations and accounts payable. Accounts payable of enterprises that have arisen to suppliers for goods (works, services) under contracts that are not registered and not accounted for in treasury departments are not covered.

Accounting operations related to the coverage of accounts payable of enterprises are carried out in accordance with the "Instructions on accounting in budgetary organizations" approved by Order of the Minister of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 17.12.2010 No. 105 (registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on 22.12.2010, No. 2169), "Regulations on accounting of income and expenses of enterprises", approved by By Order of the Minister of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 05.10.2012 No. 74, (registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on 13.11.2012 No. 2400).

Due to the fact that operations performed in an additional period of time to the financial year and related to the treasury execution of the state budget are related to the budget execution of the past year, they must be reflected in the accounting records and reports of accounting organizations for the past year, that is, accounts payable paid in January of the following year are included in the operation of the month of December last year.

In case of disagreements on accounts receivable and accounts payable, in order to eliminate them, the organization is obliged to submit materials on disagreements to the relevant authorities. Other accounts payable with expired statute of limitations are written off in accordance with the procedure established by the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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